

The Pursuit for Digitally-Supported Competitiveness of Small Businesses: Drivers, Barriers, and Future Research Streams

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Abstract. The paper presents a literature review on the drivers and barriers to digitalization and digital transformation in micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises. After a rigorous literature search and screening procedure, a bibliometric analysis was conducted on 545 papers from the Web of Science Core Collection. In the second phase of the research, 46 of the most cited papers were selected on which the full-text analysis was performed. Bibliometric analysis reveals the propulsive nature of the knowledge field, with an average annual paper growth rate of 12.74%. However, significant growth in publication productivity is a recent trend, given that the average age of the papers is slightly less than three years. In terms of country representation, there are two main clusters: a European one led by Italy and the UK, and an Asian group led by China. Insights into the conceptual and temporal structure of the field reveal the recent surge in popularity of topics related to artificial intelligence, supply chains, business models, and digital platforms. The most frequently discussed triggers of the digitalization and digital transformation of small businesses are market-related factors, like competition pressures, customer demands, and internationalization. On the other hand, psychological and organizational challenges and financial limitations stand out among the barriers. Based on the results, the conclusion discusses research gaps and implications for future studies.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Digitalization, Micro, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs), Small Business, Literature Review.

1 Introduction

During the last decades, digitalization and digital transformation have gained increasing momentum in the business world [1] and become an indispensable factors in the survival of many companies [2]. Digitalization can be understood as “the manifold sociotechnical phenomena and processes of adopting and using these technologies in broader individual, organizational, and societal contexts” [3] (p. 301). It is a two-dimensional construct because, in addition to the technical aspect related to digitization, it also includes a social component. Digital transformation (DT), on the other hand, is a broader concept that refers to directing an individual organization towards business

adaptation and strategic changes [4]. According to Vial (2019) [1], DT can be defined as “a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies”. DT actually refers to a process that uses technology as a resource to develop new business processes, software, and models with the aim of increasing a firm's profitability and competitive advantage [1]. When considering the drivers and barriers to digitalization and digital transformation, micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) have a special place. With a share of 99.8% of the total number of enterprises, MSMEs are the economic pillar of the European Union. In 2024, 26.1 million MSMEs operated in the EU-27, with 53.6% of the value added created and 65.1% of total employment in the non-financial sector [5]. However, as a result of the lack of financial and human resources and other constraints, they adopt digital technologies at a smaller and slower pace than that of large enterprises [6]. According to the latest data from the European Union, in 2024, 72.91% of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have a basic level of digital intensity, with large variations among member states. While in Denmark and Finland this share exceeds 90%, in Latvia, Hungary, Greece, and Bulgaria it is less than 60%. When it comes to certain types of digital technology, artificial intelligence (AI) has recently attracted attention. On average, AI was used by only 12.64% of EU SMEs in 2024, with 11 member states where this percentage was less than 10%. For comparison, the same EU-average share for large companies was 41.17% [7]. Given the role of digital technologies in the competitiveness of MSMEs, continued research efforts in analyzing the drivers and barriers of digitalization and digital transformation are of paramount importance. Identifying unfilled knowledge gaps and implications for future research at a time of increasing popularity and availability of technologies such as big data and generative AI are important steps in further developing the research field.

In this paper, we are searching for answers to the following research questions: *What is the intellectual and conceptual structure of the field of knowledge related to drivers and barriers to the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs? What drivers and barriers to the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs have been investigated in the relevant literature so far?* The ultimate purpose is to identify research gaps and provide suggestions for future research in the area. The research questions were examined through a literature review conducted by combining bibliometric analysis with full-text review insights. In Section 2, we describe the methodology of literature review elaborated in several stages, from searching the documents and screening procedures to data extraction and synthesis. Section 3 discusses the results of the research. Finally, in Section 4, concluding thoughts with future research streams and limitations of the review are elaborated.

2 Methodology

The methodology is based on a combination of two research methods, bibliometric analysis and systematic literature review. The protocol used followed the steps recommended in [8]. The research process began with a literature search performed in the

Web of Science Core Collection (WoS CC). The WoS CC database was selected for the research for its comprehensiveness and high level of scientific relevance [9]. The search was conducted using the "Topic" criteria with a search query based on the Boolean operators AND and OR, quotation marks for phrase searching, and the wildcard character "*", in accordance with the WoS CC syntax [10]. The export of data from the WoS CC database was carried out in January 2025. The keywords used in the query were generated based on a review of existing literature [11, 12] and a pilot search of WoS CC. As can be seen in Table 1, barriers and drivers to digitalization and digital transformation were covered by eight keywords, digitalization and digital transformation by three keywords, and MSMEs by a total of 16 keywords.

Table 1. Data about the literature search and screening procedure.

Description	No. of documents
Search query (search by <i>Topic</i>): (barrier* OR obstacle* OR challenge* OR incentive* OR driver* OR stimul* OR motivat* OR encourage*) AND (digital* OR "industry 4,0*" OR "4IR") AND ("micro business*" OR "micro firm*" OR "micro compan*" OR "micro enterpris*" OR "small business*" OR "small firm*" OR "small compan*" OR "small enterpris*" OR "sme" OR "smes" OR "msme" OR "msmes" OR "medium-sized business*" OR "medium-sized firm*" OR "medium-sized compan*" OR "medium-sized enterpris*")	1,889
Filter: Language, include only documents in English	1,841
Filter: Document Type, exclude Editorial Material, Data paper, Book Chapter, Proceeding Paper, Retracted Publication	1,378
Filter: WOS Index, exclude Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)	845
Excluded by screening (reading title, abstract and keywords)	(300)
Remaining for bibliometric analysis	545
Documents with amortized local citation less than 1.29	(499)
Remaining for SLR	46

The following three criteria for inclusion and exclusion were used: 1) Language: including only papers in English, 2) Document type: excluding editorial material, data papers, proceeding papers, book chapters, and retracted publications, and 3) WoS Index: excluding papers indexed in Emerging Source Citation Index (ESCI). The use of the second and third filters ensured a focus on peer-reviewed papers that are considered the highest quality scientific contributions. This excluded from the sample "gray" literature and papers in ESCI journals whose quality, methodological foundation, and scientific relevance vary and do not guarantee the same level of reliability as the articles included in the sample [13]. After applying the filter, 845 documents remained for screening of titles, abstracts, and keywords. In this stage, the relevance of each paper was determined in the context of barriers and drivers for MSMEs' digital transformation. The screening resulted in a sample of 545 papers for bibliometric analysis, which was performed using VOSviewer [14] and Bibliometrix (R package) [15]. All

steps of the literature search and screening process, data extraction, and analysis are schematically shown in Fig. 1.

The next step was to identify the papers on which the SLR was conducted. The aim was to further narrow the sample to the most cited publications with the greatest scientific impact. The amortized number of local citations was used as a criterion in accordance with the methodology for calculating the amortized h -index proposed by [9]. The threshold value of the amortized local citation was determined as follows: (1) values above 1 and the first two such values that differed were identified; (2) the average value of the values from point (1) was calculated, which was 1.29; (3) the value from point (2) was taken as a comprehensive fixed point for filtering articles that will be included in further phases of the research – all articles with amortized local citations above this value were included in the SLR.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of literature review procedures.

Data extraction was performed from the thus determined sample of 46 papers. In the synthesis phase of the extracted data, qualitative and quantitative analyses of the identified indicators were performed. Qualitative analysis identified and synthesized various drivers and barriers to the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs. Quantitative analysis identified the frequency of occurrence of each of these factors in the sample.

3 Results of the Review

3.1 Intellectual and Conceptual Structure of the Knowledge Field

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for the papers and authors included in the bibliometric analysis. A total of 545 papers were published in 201 journals with 32,682 references (or approx. 60 references per paper). The average age of the paper is 2.77 years, while the average annual growth rate of the paper is 12.74, which indicates the recent popularity of the knowledge field. The papers in the sample were written by a total of 1,789 authors, with 37 papers with only one author. The average number of authors per paper is 3.57, which is a figure that corresponds to the usual rate of the number of authors per paper [16]. The percentage of international collaboration is also significant (37.25%). The trend can be attributed to the field of economics and business, which has a high percentage of international collaboration that has increased over the years, unlike some other scientific fields [17].

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of papers, authors, and collaborations.

Indicator	Value	Indicator	Value
Number of sources	201	Number of citations	32,682
Number of papers	545	Number of authors	1,789
Ann. growth rate of papers	12.74%	Number of papers with one author	37
Average age of papers	2.77	Number of authors per paper	3.57
Average citations per paper	29.96	International collaboration	37.25

In Fig. 2, the annual production of the field is shown. The observation period extends from 2003 to 2025, with the data for 2025 being incomplete. Until 2017, the field was in its infancy, after which significant growth began in 2018, with the peak in 2024.

Fig. 2. Annual scientific production of the field (data for 2025 is incomplete).

Therefore, the research field has been developing at a very high rate in the last few years and is becoming increasingly popular. The trend can be linked to the average age of the paper of only 2.77 years.

In terms of the number of authors, important countries in the field are Italy, China, and the United Kingdom. As the data from Fig. 3 shows, three clusters stand out, which gather the largest number of countries. The blue cluster is a network of cooperation led by Italy, the United Kingdom, and France, and mainly includes European countries. The purple cluster brings together Asian countries, led by China and India. The third cluster (brown) refers to five European countries, with Spain at the center. Although China stands out in the collaboration network as the leader in the number of papers among Asian countries, according to the citation indicator, it is in fourth place. The UK, Italy, and Germany are more influential countries in terms of citations.

Fig. 3. Collaboration network by authors' country.

With regard to the number of citations, the United Kingdom dominates among the countries, while an important place belongs to Italy, China, and the USA (Table 3). The deviation from the findings in Fig. 3 represents Germany's third place in the number of citations, although it is not among the leaders in collaboration networks. Table 3 also shows the most relevant affiliations, or the top five institutions from which the authors of the papers included in this research come. According to the results, the Indian Institute of Management has the largest number of documents. In general, Indian, Chinese, and Italian universities, along with the University of Cambridge, are the most relevant institutions in terms of the number of papers. These results can be linked to the previously analyzed data regarding the top five most cited countries.

Related to the journal relevance in terms of citations, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, an Elsevier journal focused on papers in the field of social, environmental and technological factors [18], ranks first (Table 4). This journal is also relevant in terms of the number of papers published, ranking second behind *Sustainability*.

Therefore, the latter journal, published by the Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI) [19], with 75 documents, is the first in terms of the number of papers in the field. The reputable journals *Journal of Business Research* and *Journal of Cleaner Production* by Elsevier, and *International Journal of Production Research* by Taylor and Francis, also stand out in terms of the number of citations. Although these journals are not among the leaders in terms of the number of papers, the citation counts give them an important role in the field.

Table 3. Most relevant affiliations by number of papers and the most relevant countries by number of local citations.

Most relevant affiliations	No. p.	Most relevant countries	No. cit.
Indian Institute of Management	17	United Kingdom	3,030
University of Turin	9	Italy	1,523
Indian Institute of Management Mumbai	8	Germany	1,503
University of Cambridge	8	China	1,284
Hong Kong Polytechnic University	7	United States of America	1,158
Peking University	7		
Polytechnic University of Milan	7		
University of Pisa	7		

Additionally, Table 4 shows the most significant authors by local citation indicator. The first place is shared by four authors with 59 local citations, which refer to two papers published in their co-authorship. The papers deal with the implementation of smart manufacturing in SMEs concerning their business requirements. Their research is based on the real challenges and needs faced by SMEs engaged in manufacturing to provide proposals for improving the current state of small businesses [20, 21].

Table 4. Top 5 journals and authors by number of local citations.

Most cited journals	No. cit.	Most cited authors	No. cit.
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	1,123	Muztoba Ahmad Khan	59
Journal of Business Research	1,031	Sameer Mittal	59
Sustainability	906	David Romero	59
Journal of Cleaner Production	698	Thorsten Wuest	59
International Journal of Production Research	499	Kai-Ingo Voigt	54

Table 5 shows the top 5 papers by number of global citations. The first paper with the highest global citations is the work by E. Autio and associates published in 2018. The paper has 766 global citations, which indicates the high relevance and usefulness in the field. It is based on a clear distinction of entrepreneurial systems from typical traditional clusters with an emphasis on exploiting entrepreneurial opportunities and digital opportunities [22]. Another work with 648 global citations is the paper of the author J. M. Müller and the co-author of the title *Fortune Favors the Prepared: How SMEs approach business model innovations in Industry 4.0*, published in 2018. The paper examines the

impact of Industry 4.0 on small and medium-sized enterprises in production, in the form of initiating changes in their business models. The authors conducted a qualitative study on a sample of 68 German SMEs from three industries [23]. The third paper has 572 global citations, and the title of the paper is A critical review of smart manufacturing & Industry 4.0 maturity models: Implications for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by S. Mittal and associates from 2018. This paper compares the currently available maturity models of smart manufacturing and Industry 4.0 and aligns their characteristics with the requirements of SMEs [21].

Table 5. Top 5 papers by number of global citations.

Most cited papers	No. cit.
Autio, E. et al.; 2018; Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal	766
Müller, J. M. et al.; 2018; Technological Forecasting and Social Change	648
Mittal, S. et al.; 2018; Journal of Manufacturing Systems	572
Coreynen, W.; 2018; Industrial Marketing Management	440
Wong, L. W.; 2020; International Journal of Information Management	404

Table 6 shows the most significant words extracted from the abstracts of the papers. The significance of the words is represented by the frequency of their occurrence in the papers. The keywords are related to terms that are generally related to the topic, such as digital transformation, small and medium-sized enterprises and digital technologies. The concepts of supply chain, business model, and digital platforms play an important role. The topics related to these concepts are significant, that is, there is a large number of researchers in the field who deal with issues of supply chains and digital platforms.

Table 6. The most relevant words according to frequency of appearance in abstracts.

Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
digital transformation	419	supply chain	91
enterprises SMEs	234	business model	68
medium-sized enterprises	203	digital technology	55
digital technologies	143	business models	52
medium enterprises	96	digital platforms	52

Fig. 4 illustrates the co-occurrence network of author keywords and keywords plus. The network was generated using the full counting method and with a minimum number of keyword occurrences of 10. Four thematic clusters can be identified. Innovation, management, performance, and digital transformation are the key concepts of the red cluster. The cluster represents research with theoretical origins in strategic management, especially the dynamic capabilities and the resource-based view of the firm. As part of this stream, digital technology is considered as an element of building a company's competitive advantage that affects value creation, growth and other aspects of business performance. The green cluster includes a corpus of works related to the barriers to the introduction of Industry 4.0 in MSMEs, with frequent consideration of collaborations

and supply chains. The specific aspects of this cluster relate to research into the adoption of artificial intelligence, big data and the Internet of Things, as well as the implementation of smart production, and Industry 4.0 in the function of circular economy and sustainability. The blue cluster covers research on MSMEs in the context of drivers of business model innovation, with consideration of e-commerce and social networks as specific forms of DT. Finally, the yellow cluster includes research on the determinants of technology acceptance and technology adoption in MSMEs.

Fig. 4. All keyword co-occurrence network-visualization.

Fig. 5 shows the conceptual development of the field. The observation time is divided into four periods. For each period, dominant concepts are shown, and the transition between periods suggests the field's evolution. In the period up to 2010, the field was in its infancy and conceptually poor, with the digital divide as the only prominent topic.

Fig. 5. Thematic evolution of the field.

From 2011 to 2020, significant progress was made, with the most significant concepts being related to the study of innovation processes in MSMEs, the creation of new business models, and the digitalization of production. In addition to production processes, topics related to digital marketing are gaining popularity. The period 2021-2024 is marked by conceptual consolidation, with the emergence of new topics, such as the digitalization of supply chains (SC) (which is potentially based on the issue of SC disruptions during the COVID-19 pandemic [24]). Recently, in addition to business models, the topic of using artificial intelligence in MSMEs has been explored.

3.2 Drivers and Barriers to the Digitalization and Digital Transformation

Of the total of 46 papers included in the SLR, 34 (73.91%) are empirical research, and 12 (26.09%) are conceptual and review papers. Regarding the methodology, out of 34 empirical papers, 19 (55.88%) used a quantitative approach, 12 (35.29%) a qualitative approach, and 3 (8.82%) a mixed-method framework. Speaking of the industry in which the research was conducted, manufacturing predominates, with a smaller portion of the work focused on service industries. Regarding the geographical aspect of the research, half of the papers focused on countries on the European continent, while Asian countries, India, and the United States were significantly less represented. The trend can be attributed to the greater presence and promotion of SMEs in the European region, making it more suitable for research. The most common theories represented in the papers are the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework [25], the resource-based theory [26], and the dynamic capabilities approach [27].

Considering the objectives of research included in the SLR, the works can be divided into several categories. The first category addresses the adoption of technologies and innovations in the context of implementing Industry 4.0, AI, and big data analytics. The second category of papers focuses on the inclusion of organizational and human factors in digital transformation, covering topics such as project-based learning, managers' perceptions, internal obstacles and/or drivers for business changes, and the adaptation of organizational culture to the digitalization processes. There is also a group of studies focused on internationalization in the context of digital technology, dealing with the global expansion of SMEs and the role of technology in international operations. Part of the papers investigates frameworks for the implementation of digital transformation in small businesses and digital maturity within Industry 4.0 and 5.0. Finally, there is the topic of barriers and opportunities in the markets that small businesses may encounter, and issues of using technologies in the context of sustainable development.

The central part of the SLR was the identification of drivers and barriers to the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs. Fig. 6 shows the identified drivers with their corresponding frequencies of occurrence in the texts. The drivers found are categorized into four groups: (1) market-related factors, (2) efficiency, productivity, and cost reduction factors, (3) state support factors, and (4) other factors. Market-related factors are the most frequent and include issues related to customers, competition, and internationalization. Digital transformation is considered a lever for improving the visibility and competitiveness of companies in the international market, as well as engagement of customers through digital channels and their greater integration. Important

aspects considered here also are the adequate response of MSMEs to the numerous changes occurring in the environment and adaptation to diverse customer requirements. The next category of factors is related to the goals of increasing efficiency, reducing costs, and exploiting new technologies for operational improvements. The latest digital technology in this context is viewed as a means to enhance the business performance of companies. Other external and internal factors are also included. Regarding the external ones, government support in the form of incentives is highlighted, as well as factors such as compliance with legal requirements and stakeholder pressures. Among the factors that arise within the company, management support and the need to improve flexibility, communication, and decision-making processes are highlighted.

Fig. 6. Drivers to the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs with the frequencies of occurrence in the texts, identified by the SLR.

The barriers to digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs are categorized into the following groups: (1) psychological and organizational factors, (2) financial factors and other resources, (3) knowledge and skills factors, (4) technology factors and (un)perceiving benefits, (5) security, trust, and other factors (Fig. 7). Considering the frequency of occurrence, the most important are psychological and organizational factors, related to challenges in organizational culture and employee participation, internal resistance to change, and lack of management support and technology awareness. Limited resources, financial risks, and high costs are barriers related to financial and other resources. In particular, human resource constraints are highlighted, with the manifestation in limited availability of talent and lack of technological expertise and complementary knowledge. Technology infrastructure factors are related to technological limitations, challenges and risks, and also include technology complexity, lack of access to high-speed digital infrastructure, and immature IT infrastructure. Non-understanding of benefits and uncertainty about the return on investment in technologies are another category of potential constraints. Finally, the analysis of barriers must not ignore factors of distrust concerning cyber risks, especially information security and protection.

Fig. 7. Barriers to the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs with the frequencies of occurrence in the texts, identified by the SLR.

4 Conclusion

The paper reviewed the literature on drivers and barriers for digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs. As is found, the research field has been developing rapidly, gaining increasing popularity in the last few years. Insights into the intellectual and conceptual structure of the field reveal a gradual conceptual consolidation, with a recent higher representation of topics related to business models, supply chains, digital platforms, and AI. The most important drivers of the digitalization and digital transformation of MSMEs are competitive pressures, customer demands, internationalization, and other market-related factors. Among the barriers, psychological and organizational challenges, and limited financial resources stand out. Based on the results, the following research gaps and implications for future studies are identified:

- Although Asian countries, led by China and India, produce a lot of work in the field, their relevance measured by citations is significantly lower compared to the works of European authors. It is necessary to improve the relevance of studies conducted outside Europe, and to redirect the research focus to other spatial contexts.
- From a methodological perspective, very little research is based on a mixed-method approach. More comprehensive studies are needed that combine capturing in-depth, qualitative understandings from the perspective of small business owners with quantitative analyses on large samples, within the same research project.
- The field could benefit from supplementing popular theoretical foundations (TOE framework, resource-based theory, dynamic capabilities) with new conceptual lenses. One of the promising perspectives in the context of entrepreneurship and small business could be the external enabler theory by Davidsson et al. (2020) [28].
- More research is needed on the issue of drivers and barriers to the application of generative AI in MSMEs. Factors related to technology anxiety, concerns about hallucinations, and AI conspiracy beliefs [29] deserve more attention. The challenges associated with recognizing the benefits of generative AI as support for certain types of business tasks are also a relevant topic for future research.
- More research is needed in service sectors, given the dominance of manufacturing small businesses in the sub-sample of empirical studies.

Only papers from the WoS CC database are included in this literature review. Future reviews should include other relevant databases, such as Scopus. The research limitation also stems from the exclusion of “grey” literature and papers from ESCI journals from the sample. However, such filtering is not unjustified, since it enabled consideration of only peer-reviewed, high-quality scientific material [13].

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Authors' background

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